

ENHANCING DATA SECURITY IN SALESFORCE USING SHIELD PLATFORM ENCRYPTION

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ABSTRACT

This is where the use of Shield Platform Encryption to strengthen data security on Salesforce comes in handy especially for compliance with laws such as GDPR and HIPAA. Based on the results, Shield scrambles data stored on the platform so that they cannot be read if stolen and integrates with the Salesforce environment. For security reasons Shield has to be combined with OwnBackup for backed up encrypted data and Data Mask for anonymizing data for sandboxing. All together these tools contribute to strong security environment and safeguards data from the time it is produced, developed and in response to regulatory requirements.

Keywords: Data Security, Cloud Platform, Symmetric Encryption, Asymmetric Encryption, Multi-Factor Authentication.

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INTRODUCTION

Data security is crucial in Salesforce, as it stores data and business processes. Lack of proper data security may lead to a data breach, which includes loss of finances and tarnishing of the company's reputation, which would further have legal implications for the data. According to an IBM report on the Cost of a Data Breach (2023), the global average cost of data breaches stands at \$4.45 million, showing its scalability and possible effects on businesses [6].

Salesforce incorporates customer relationship management CRMs, which makes it a store for sensitive information. Preserving this data is crucial to upholding the customer trust vested in the companies [1]. Due to the rising threats in the online business environment, companies are at risk from phishing, insider threats, and ransomware. According to Verizon's 2023 Data Breach Investigations Report, several risks are still associated with cyber attacks [7].

The report poses 83% of data breaches originated from outside the organizations, and 74% were financial. Therefore, the adoption of Salesforce makes the organization secure as it uses a complex protection strategy to reduce risks through encryption, user authorization, and tracking. However, companies still need to employ extra measures that include password protection, regular audit assessments, and users' awareness to ensure they are totally aware of the system's security [9].

Organizations need to set up proper security measures and uphold compliance. This penalizes institutions since GDPR and CCPA penalize firms for handling data inappropriately[29].The things that require protection are the company's data. This means that data security in Salesforce is one of the most important aspects of an effective business and long-term success [2].

Shield Platform Encryption is one of the security measures implemented within Salesforce to protect data at rest. Encrypting data will mitigate unauthorized access since it will be in an encrypted form, which cannot be understood by anyone who is not authenticated to access it. This is especially important in businesses with sensitive information that needs protection, such as the financial sector, health sector, and governmental institutions [3].

According to Kerckhoff's theorem, the inaccessibility of the key to encryption rather than the algorithm should manifest the given system's security level. Shield follows this principle by employing secure encryption procedures such as AES-256, which are very safe. Shield enables organizations to control their keys[12]. The system is still preserved safely despite being easily understandable by network users so long as the security of the key can be enhanced.

Shield Platform Encryption also comes in handy regarding GDPR and HIPAA compliance by protecting data and guaranteeing data security in its lifecycle. It is possible to have the visibility and decryption of the information controlled by organizations, with the encrypted content accessed only by the right users [14]. Moreover, Shield Platform Encryption businesses integrate an additional layer of security into their Salesforce environment and mitigate risks that come with data leakage and hacking.

Problem statement.

(i) To protect sensitive Data at Rest: Shield Platform Encryption provides security for data, including, but not limited to, financial and health information, by encrypting it within Salesforce. Hence, organizations will reduce the exposure of data in case data storage is compromised.

(ii) To support regulatory compliance: Shield is a compliance program that assists organizations in achieving some regulatory requirements. Encrypting data and controlling decryption, the legal requirements that govern the protection of personal and sensitive data are met, avoiding expensive penalties and other possible legal implications [3].

(iii) Enhance Access Control and Data Privacy: Using Shield, organizations can deploy per-file control on who gets access and decryption rights over significant data. Shield also enables businesses to control their encryption keys, which adds extra strength to their data protection against violators since it is hard to duplicate a key owned by someone [25].

Objectives of the study

Salesforce user data is directly compromised by security risks such as data leakage, hacking of the user account, and non-compliance. Traditional practices include a firewall and access control that does not protect data at rest, making it vulnerable to internal and external threats. Shield platform encryption meets this need by building an encryption shield that would envelop the data at rest in Salesforce and is only accessible to holders of the decryption key [13].

This reduces the risks and cases of breaches. This enhances compliance since regulated data is shielded from loss by handling matters concerning data security to prevent data breaches or unauthorized access.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Data security is critical in managing CRM systems such as Salesforce, where customer details, vendors, their records, financial information, and business processes are available and processed. Since increasing numbers of businesses use cloud platforms, protecting and securing this data against cyber attacks, unauthorized access, and compliance issues have become a problem [2].

Security issues such as compromised data and unauthorized access are among the most contentious issues between organizations and Salesforce. According to Verizon Data Breach Investigations Report 2023, external account compromise was identified in 83% of breaches, and 74% of the cyber security breaches were committed by cyber attackers for financial gain[14-16]. This is because the system deployed had vulnerabilities due to unrestricted access controls comprised of misconfigurations, weak passwords, and ineffective user authentication, exposing sensitive information to the digital assailant [6].

High-risk firms that deal with sensitive customer data must adhere to specific legal obligations, which include but are not limited to GDPR, CCPA, and HIPAA. The study shows that failure to meet the above requirements results in severe penalties and reputational loss. Users of Salesforce are left with the daunting task of ensuring that they abide by these legal requirements on data protection in most cases where data is distributed across different regions [8].

One of the most significant risks in Salesforce environments is insider threats. According to a cybersecurity insider report, trusted insider threats occasion 60% of organizations' threats as they are the main challenge for data security [26]. Those users with special permissions to access the system and work with the data can cause intentional or unintentional leakage or modification of data. Keeping track of data and regulating the privilege of data privacy in an organization must be handled with absolute care.

Phishing and social engineering attacks have significantly increased in recent years, with most malicious actors attempting to perpetrate unauthorized access to Salesforce users' accounts. According to the IBM X-Force Threat Intelligence Index (2023), phishing tops the list as the most prevalent method of attack, taking 41% of the attacks. People's psychological engineering is used instead of the organization's technical flaws. Therefore, such threats can hardly be eradicated even for complicated platforms like Salesforce [13].

Data Security Solutions in Salesforce

One of the most secure features offered by Salesforce is the Shield Platform Encryption, which provides data encryption at rest using the AES-256 encryption standards [15]. Shield also helps encrypt any business's standard data while preserving attributes such as business process automation in Salesforce. This encryption complies with Kerckhoffs's Principle, which states that the security in the system depends on the confidentiality of the key and not the mechanism of the key.

Multi-factor authentication (MFA) is the key issue and solution that reduces the risks of unauthorized access to Salesforce. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) is considered a critical solution [5]. MFA enhances security through two- or multi-factor verification and ensures that they are provided first before they are given access. Therefore, applying MFA can significantly reduce the chances of account breaches.

According to a Google security report, MFA can prevent 99.9% of automated attacks. This makes it difficult for attacks such as DoS and brute force to be launched [4].

Event Monitoring and Auditing: Salesforce offers Event Monitoring in the Shield set, enabling organizations to monitor user activity, including suspicious activities. For instance, Privileged User Monitoring, suggested in the NIST Cybersecurity Framework, is one method that allows an organization to detect when users interact with the data. Access logs should be audited regularly to give an immediate response in case of a security breach [16].

Data Masking and Tokenization: Data masking is another rising solution for data protection in Salesforce. It swaps the actual data with absolute values. Only authorized people, such as administrators and super users, can see the exact data, while other personnel involved in the application's development and testing cannot access it. Data masking is on the rise and is mainly used to comply with privacy regulations and mitigate insider threats [6].

Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): Salesforce uses and recommends Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) to control data security. This way, an organization can restrict employees' access to particular data based on the principle of least privilege after providing accounts to each user with specific rights. According to the SANS Institute, proper RBAC can decrease the attack surface since users get access only to the data required [17].

Discuss encryption methodologies and how Shield Platform Encryption addresses these issues.

Encryption methodologies are core concepts in data security since they can convert readable information (plaintext) into a form everyone cannot access (ciphertext). Different methods of encrypting are used depending on the level of protection needed in the organization.

Symmetric Encryption is used in the ciphering and deciphering process. This method is usually used and is very efficient with many data encryptions [19]. However, key management can be problematic because the key needs to be shared securely amongst multiple parties, especially where the environment is distributed. There has been no crucial change in this kind of encryption. However, some standard symmetric encryption algorithms include AES [20].

Asymmetric encryption involves using two other keys: a public key for encrypting the data and a secret or private key for decrypting the data. This results in savings on the encryption key, but the process is computationally expensive. RSA (Rivest–Shamir—Adleman) is a familiar asymmetric algorithm employed when it is necessary to protect communication channels [11].

Unlike irreversible encryption, hashing transforms data into a string of characters of equal length. Hashing is used for data integrity checking, but it is unsuitable for encryption since it cannot be decrypted.

Salesforce Shield Platform Encryption uses AES-256 symmetric encryption, which shields data at rest. This encryption standard is relatively well-known for its middle-of-the-road security and performance characteristics, which allow technology to encrypt large data sets, especially in Salesforce environments. With Shield features, data stored in fields, files, and attachments is encrypted. Search capability and workflow automation technology remain, so encrypted data is functional [5].

Shield enables organizations to manage encryption keys with a BYOD key model. This model encrypts data and ensures that only those entitled can decrypt it, making it more secure than previous protocols.

METHODOLOGY

Methods to Assess Shield Platform Encryption's Impact on Security

Data Encryption Monitoring

To ensure the effectiveness of using Shield Platform Encryption, one has to monitor the data being encrypted continuously. This ensures compliance with certain data encryption standards and that data in transit and at rest is encrypted. This will also entail verifying that the correct encryption algorithms have been used.

Access control and auditing:

The Shield Platform Encryption can be effectively implemented with Salesforce's Event Monitoring to simultaneously track data movement and user activity. This helps determine an intrusion into encrypted data so the organization can set threshold values. Implementing role-based access control will ensure only the relevant users can view or edit what they have access to [8].

Salesforce Data Mask

Salesforce Data Mask is a tool that allows organizations to mask all or part of the sandbox. This approach complements Shield Platform Encryption by ensuring data security in environments other than production where encryption may not be involved [11].

OwnSecure is a concept initially developed for simplifying salesforce security management.

OwnSecure is one of the tools that own uses to enhance the security of Salesforce when dealing with vulnerability scanning. This will encompass scanning different weaknesses in the system, such as security settings and user permissions, to identify if a vulnerability exists and ensure that the system is effective in an appropriate manner. However, though it is directly involved with data encryption, it contributes to the general improvement of the security trends in the platform.

Tools Work Together for Enhanced Security.

- (i) Encryption and Masking: Shield Platform Encryption deals with data encryption for data rest, whereas Data Mask ensures data in development and test environments are protected. These two approaches automatically enhance data security and ensure minimal data leakage.
- (ii) Proactive Security Monitoring: OwnSecure ensures that the settings around encrypted data are correctly locked, while Shield Platform Encryption is responsible for encrypting the data. Event monitoring effectively records access to encrypted fields to alert the user, which is more effective than waiting for compliance breaches [18].

IMPLEMENTATION

A business case for applying Shield Platform Encryption in Salesforce is the encryption of customer-sensitive information, such as SSNs and credit card information, stored in custom and standard fields. Data transmitted, for instance, for financial services firms, are encrypted with Shield to meet regulations like GDPR and HIPAA [11].

OwnBackup creates backup copies of encrypted data, and no data is lost in case of failure or deletion by a user. Backups are also encrypted to ensure they are as secure as the production environment. A salesforce data mask is used in the sandbox to ensure data security during the development and testing process[27]. This will encompass replacing actual SSNs with zeroes in numbers. This allows elopers to work with the actual data, yet the customer's information is completely inaccurate [10].

Shield is more used in the real sense by companies such as healthcare firms to encrypt patient health records and Data Mask to ensure compliance in dev and test instances. Samples of best practices are the periodic review of the encryption key management policies, the need to ensure that data in the sandbox are anonymized, and the use of OwnBackup for automated backup against data loss and breach [15].This ensures that data is protected across different environments, giving the system a strong base.

RESULTS

Data such as medical record history or insurance information can be saved in the Salesforce system, which helps protect sensitive information. The security of the Salesforce database is guaranteed even where intruders have compromised it. The attacker will not be able to access the encrypted fields without decryption keys [12]. This helps safeguard sensitive data in case of an attack or data breach.

Businesses that deal with voluminous customers' personal information, such as customers' card numbers and purchasing histories, require a complete mechanism in which the customer's data can be safeguarded. This will encompass deploying shield encryption to enhance the encryption of each piece of financial data in the database and other system interfaces. Thus improving the system's security [18]. Even in cases where the server is compromised, the attacker will never decipher any readable financial information. Therefore, the salesforce data mask being deployed in the company's sandbox environment as masked financial information enables the developers to work on the system without compromising customers.

OwnBackup provides encrypted backup and guarantees that encrypted data will not be lost during system failures[28]. This may demonstrate the effectiveness of these tools in terms of ROI. This decreases the likelihood of digital assailants compromising sensitive information during sandbox development and improves more than 50% faster disaster recovery owing to automated tools for data backup [21].

These tools help multinational corporations comply 100% with regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA. Shield Encryption, Data Masking, and OwnBackup provide a complete solution that significantly minimizes the potential for data threats and secures data integrity in Salesforce implementations [13].

DISCUSSION

Integrating with other tools such as OwnBackup, Data Mask, and Shield Platform Encryption can provide adequate security solutions for Salesforce. This will enhance Salesforce's capability by providing an all-in-plan Shield Platform Encryption [21]. Most organizations use third-party encryption solutions or have cumbersome essential management procedures, whereas Shield Platform Encryption provides encryption inside Salesforce. This is opposed to standard encryption services that may come with various intricate and extra software that can cause challenges to the security management framework.

Historical and conventional solutions to data protection, such as firewalls and network monitoring, which form the first lines of defense in any network environment, protect an organization from external attacks but fail when an internal attacker or an external actor gets into the system. Shield Platform Encryption avoids this by encrypting data at rest. Therefore, if the data is compromised, unauthorized parties cannot access the information [23].

The study presupposes that by integrating OwnBackup into Shield platform encryption, organizations place another layer that involves encrypted automatic backups. This reduces the risk of data loss, especially in disasters or system crashes, while personal information is safeguarded in both normal and backup. Traditional backup solutions do not encrypt the backup data, leaving it open to attacks during a breach [9].

In non-production environments, many different sorts of data remain unfamiliar and unsecured because security measures are not properly implemented. Salesforce Data Mask, therefore, is considered a complete safeguard for the data as real data is not copied to sandbox environments that can be intercepted and exploited [22]. This helps reduce the data breach and leak that could have happened during the development or testing phase by as much as 90%, a higher threshold than could not be achieved through encryption only.

CONCLUSION

Salesforce Shield Platform Encryption and other tools such as Own Backup and Salesforce Data Mask protect shareholders' information in Salesforce. Shield Platform Encryption safeguards data at rest, thus maintaining proper security in case an attacker has external aggression into the system [25]. Data Mask is an important aspect of this study as it demonstrates how sandbox environments where data is used to develop and test are masked to prevent exposure of vital data if an application fails in other environments [19].

Production data protection yields an end-to-end solution, which is different from classical encryption approaches covering non-production environments. The outcome is better as there is adherence to rules and regulations. This implies higher data quality and lower susceptibility to data breaches.

The study significantly impacts the data security of organizations that adopt Salesforce Shield platform encryption. This is because the organization benefits from effective event monitoring, field audits, and enhanced platform encryption. This is because implementing all measures will improve the security of data at rest through platform encryption as it ensures sensitive data remains secure and will help one stay safe from unauthorized access. A field audit trial will enhance the security of the company's data as standard retention limits will ensure the company keeps the data for a long time to the extent of 10 years.

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